

Effective methods of teaching French at school

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ABSTRACT

this article talks about effective methods of studying French and modern interaction methods.

Educational tasks that serve to develop students' creative thinking are given in French language textbooks of high school. These tasks should be done independently by the students in collaboration with the teacher in different ways. Grammatical games are one of the main types of tasks that give a positive result. These types of tasks require intelligence, knowledge, research, resourcefulness and speed from students. Games-tasks are very important in the interesting passage of French language learners. However, grammar games-tasks and the methodology of their use are not developed sufficiently in "Methodology of French language teaching". The peculiar aspect of games and tasks is that it is often organized in the form of a competition. As a result, giving incentives or points to students and groups will undoubtedly increase students' motivation to complete the task. As a result, students' grammatical literacy, creative thinking ability, ingenuity, speech and love for this subject will increase. At the same time, the use of additional literature creates the need to seriously engage with other disciplines. Taking this into account, it is appropriate for the teacher to effectively use various games and puzzles to make his lessons more effective. The demand of today's time also demands skill, creativity, and most importantly, tireless work from a science teacher. Taking this into account, we will consider some grammar games, puzzles and methods of their use that can be used in the transition of French language learners. You can come up with more such grammar games and use them in the course of the lesson. As mentioned above, it depends on the teacher's creativity, inquisitiveness, skills and tireless work.

1. Game tasks of recall type. Such games are used more often in the lessons of strengthening the learned topics and checking knowledge and skills. For example, in order to strengthen lessons on memorizing new words, "Who is the winner?" it is appropriate to use the game task. For this, the class is divided into two groups: the first group says French words, the second group finds the Uzbek meaning. The winner is the one who finds the most words in a given time. The teacher writes the words of fruit, vegetable, domestic animal, wild animal,

household item separately on the board. The class is divided into five groups (the number of students must be taken into account. If the number of students is not divided equally into groups, the number of groups can be reduced or increased), they are required to write examples of these nouns. Writes one example of the relative word. The group that writes quickly and correctly is considered the winner. The winners must be encouraged. Such games can be used to strengthen any topic.

Or you can play the game "The words are from us, the text is from you" in order to test the interconnected written speech of the students. In this case, students are given key words and phrases (*they can also be written on the board*) and are instructed to use them to create a connected text.

Increasing the vocabulary of students is one of the requirements of DTS, using games-tasks of the nature of inquiry is good for the development of this skill. Such assignments require students to be creative. The "Creator" game-task can be effectively used to pass the "Ravish" topic. In this grammar game, the class is divided into two groups, the first group is asked to give examples of sentences with adjectives, and the second group is asked to make a sentence by replacing the noun(s) in these sentences with adverbs. For example: A representative of the first group writes: I wrote a good essay (what kind of essay?) at the Olympiad. The second group continues: Our group participates well in it (how did it participate?). It will be continued in this way. It is possible to continue this game between students or between parallel classes in the form of "word exchange". In the process of French language learning, language phenomena are observed, compared and compared, their similarities and differences are identified, they are grouped according to their general and specific aspects, and generalization rules are created by means of the assignment system. As a result, there is a dynamic growth from recall tasks to creative tasks. Such assignments are of particular importance in the development of the student's thinking. Determining and determining the growth dynamics of educational tasks from simple to complex is a complex process. Assignments should be placed in such a way that they have a positive effect on the development of the student's thinking. Creative assignments, that is, assignments that develop the student's thinking, must have specific characteristics:

- encourage the student to search, to think, to find the unknown;
- it is necessary to direct the student to draw an independent conclusion;
- as the problem becomes more complicated, the student's mind and understanding should grow;
- the course of this process should develop students' teamwork skills;
- the process of completing the tasks must encourage the student to gain self-confidence, self-awareness (*knowledge*), ability to identify opportunities, and to acquire new knowledge.

In the textbooks created on the basis of the updated educational content, the classes for all departments of linguistics begin with the analysis of assignments for each subject without starting with definitions and rules, that is, without giving students ready-made knowledge. This is where the teacher's skill, ability, and learning are shown. In this process, a step-by-step transition from one method of activity to another, that is, from observation to grouping based on common characteristics, from repetition, generalizations are formed based on identification of similarities and differences. Only then will the assignments serve to reveal the nature of language phenomena

In linguistics, games are considered as a powerful tool for language teaching. With the help of games, pronunciation is well learned, lexical and grammatical material is activated, listening comprehension and oral speech skills are developed. The use of game methods makes it possible to involve even "weak" students in the learning process, because this method not only demonstrates knowledge in the student, but also develops creative understanding skills. In addition, a student with a weak language preparation can be the first in the process of participating in the game, where resourcefulness and understanding are important. allows

him to overcome the feeling of shyness that destroys him in learning. Such students also master the language material without realizing it, and they feel satisfied that *"I can speak a foreign language like everyone else."* Methodist scientists on foreign language teaching According to the opinion, The game consists of the following activities [2.48];

1. Type of activity (in language learning - speech)
2. Attract (without forcing);
3. Activities aimed at each person;
4. Education and training in the community through the community;
5. Development of psychological skills;
6. "Learning with pleasure

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, the issue of students' interest in the educational process, "their real participation in various events" is becoming more and more acute. This is because the main task of learning a foreign language - the ability to communicate with native speakers - is often not achieved at school. There are several reasons why students do not have enough enthusiasm and interest in learning a foreign language, and the task of every teacher is to *"maintain and increase students' interest in the lesson."* One of the ways to attract the attention of schoolchildren is non-standard forms of teaching - they *"attract the attention of students, increase their interest in science and contribute to better learning of the material."* Non-standard forms of the lesson include excursion lessons, thematic lessons, didactic games and, of course, work in groups. Active methods of language teaching, which are becoming increasingly popular, play an important role here.

Methods used in teaching French. Active teaching methods are methods that "encourage students to actively think and practice in the process of mastering educational material." N.M. Kleimenova emphasizes that "the knowledge obtained empirically is the most profound and profound." So, it is clear that in order to teach a foreign language effectively, it is necessary to organize the lesson in a different way, to attract the attention of students, and most importantly, to encourage them to learn the language independently. The passive method is a form of interaction between students and the teacher, in which the teacher is the main participant and manager of the lesson, and the students act as passive listeners, following the teacher's instructions. In passive lessons, the teacher communicates with students through inquiry, independent, control work, tests, etc. It is considered a passive method in terms of the effectiveness of modern pedagogical technologies and learning material by students the most ineffective, but nevertheless it also has some positive aspects. Active method is a form of interaction between students and teachers in which the teacher and students interact with each other during the lesson and where students they are not passive listeners, but active participants of the lesson. If in a passive lesson, the main character and leader of the lesson is the teacher, then the teacher and students have equal rights here.

Interactive method Interactive ("Inter" is mutual, "act" means to act) - to interact, to be in a conversational style. In other words, in contrast to active methods, interactive methods are focused on the wider interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other, and the dominance of student activity in the learning process.

Result When using active methods of teaching, the student's role changes - he turns from an obedient memory device to an active participant in the learning process. This new role and its characteristic features make it possible to form an active person with all the necessary skills and qualities of a modern successful person.

Interactive education for the student:

- development of personal thinking;
- awareness of participation in common work;
- forming the position of an active subject in educational activities;
- development of communication skills;
- ethical acceptance of norms and rules of joint activity;

- increasing cognitive activity;
- formation of the class as a team;
- increasing cognitive interest;
- development of analysis and introspection skills in the process of group thinking; to the teacher:
- a non-standard attitude to the organization of the educational process;
- formation of motivational readiness for interpersonal relations not only in education, but also in other situations.

Games for learning to read. The learning potential of games has been known for a long time. Many well-known teachers have rightly paid attention to the effectiveness of using games in the educational process. In the game, human abilities are especially fully and sometimes unexpectedly revealed.

Conclusion: It is well known how difficult it is to form an interest in learning the French language and then maintain it. In the past years, the competition is the English language, its demand is undeniable, development of methodological methods of work. In recent years, many teachers have been increasingly using the methodology of collaborative teaching, which is part of the project method, in their practice.

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